

The Past, Present, and Future of Dark Energy Research with NOIRLab Facilities

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This year marks the 25th anniversary of the discovery of the accelerating expansion of the Universe and the implication that it was being powered by some mysterious form of “dark energy.” There is no question that this is the most startling discovery in cosmology since 1965, when Arno Penzias and Robert Wilson discovered the cosmic microwave background, thus almost instantly establishing the Big Bang as the dominant theory of the origin of the Universe.

It has been a particular delight to me as a member of the NSF's NOIRLab scientific staff that the discovery was made by teams using NOAO telescopes and instruments.¹ Both the High-Z Supernova Search Team, led by Brian Schmidt, and the Supernova Cosmology Project, led by Saul Perlmutter, requested time through the standard open NOAO time allocation process. The famed searches for SN Ia and their photometric follow-up took place on the Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory (CTIO) Víctor M. Blanco 4-meter Telescope, enabled by a wide-field CCD camera. But well before that, both teams benefited from a plethora of precursor programs done with a variety of NOAO telescopes at both Kitt Peak National Observatory (KPNO) and CTIO, again using time awarded by the standard open time allocation process.

As they say, the rest is history. In this issue of *The Mirror*, we offer a set of science highlight articles to celebrate the role of NOAO in the discovery of dark energy as well as to describe the observational work supported by NOAO that followed, work that continues now using NOIRLab facilities. The first two articles are informal first-person histories of the High-Z Supernova Search Team by [Adam Riess and Brian Schmidt](#) and of the Supernova Cosmology Project by [Saul Perlmutter](#), all of whom in 2011 were awarded the Nobel Prize in Physics

for their discovery of the accelerating expansion of the Universe. Follow-up work in the first decade of this century drew heavily on NOAO facilities, and [Michael Wood-Vasey](#) recounts an ambitious program, done through the NOAO survey program, that provided some of the first observations tightening our understanding of the dark energy equation of state.

As was quickly realized, high-precision studies of the evolution of the dark energy equation of state over cosmological time would require new instrumentation and dedicated long-term surveys covering large fractions of the sky. The resulting Dark Energy Survey (DES) is one such example of this. The DES was a partnership between the Department of Energy (DOE)'s Fermilab and NOAO, which led to the deployment of the Dark Energy Camera at the Blanco telescope. The DES is described in the article by [Chihway Chang et al.](#)

The soon-to-be commissioned Vera C. Rubin Observatory Simonyi Survey Telescope, which will be operated by NOIRLab, was justified because of its ability to test the evolution of the dark energy equation of state over cosmological time. The Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument (DESI), developed and operated by DOE's Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, has begun operating on the KPNO Nicholas U. Mayall 4-meter Telescope. NOIRLab is providing access to DESI data to the community. NOIRLab astronomers [Stéphanie Juneau and Adam Bolton](#) summarize the DESI Early Data Release, now available for archival research. Meanwhile, [Katrin Heitmann et al.](#) describe the LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration, which will use the Telescope in a multi-pronged approach to achieve this goal.

¹The National Optical Astronomy Observatory (NOAO) joined with the International Gemini Observatory and Vera C. Rubin Observatory Operations, to become [NSF's NOIRLab in 2019](#).